

Instructors and University Professors' Perception on Knowledge Management in School Environment

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ABSTRACT

An alternative strategy that can be used by schools and universities in keeping their instructors and professors equipped with relevant skills to face challenges in improving performance as its uses in commercial sectors is Knowledge Management. However, little research has been undertaken on how knowledge management can be applied to school environment. To put knowledge management into action, it is crucial to understand teachers' perception of knowledge management at the outset. The study was carried out in a Quezon City University. Interviews, based on relevant knowledge management models, were conducted to understand the instructors

and professors' perception of knowledge management. The result of the study found that knowledge sharing, people, culture and knowledge storage with IT support were regarded as important from the interviewees' points of view. Most interviewees might accept that knowledge management can help improve their practice but it needs the support of various dimensions such as people, culture, IT and management. The findings may provide insights for knowledge management implementation in the school.

Keywords: knowledge management, higher education, teacher perception, knowledge sharing, organizational culture

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge Management is not a new concept. According to Barron (2000) it is an integrated, systematic approach to identifying, managing and sharing all of an enterprise's information assets, including databases, documents, policies and procedures, as well as previously unarticulated expertise and experience held by individual workers. A typical knowledge management process includes five stages: acquisition, refining, storage and retrieval, distribution and presentation (Zhao, 2010). Nevertheless, the nature of knowledge is complex; many people try to identify what knowledge is from different perspectives. There are two common ways to distinguish knowledge. Some scholars, like Kogut and Zander (1996), distinguish between know-what and know-how (practical knowledge) while others, like Nonaka (1994), prefer to use the distinction between tacit and explicit knowledge based on Polanyi's (1967) theory. In general, tacit knowledge is hard to articulate and transfer, and has been linked with know-how; explicit knowledge is relatively easy to articulate and codify, and has been linked with know-what.

A good knowledge management system must treat all sorts of knowledge, from know-what to know-how, and from tacit to explicit. This is the greatest difficulty for the implementation of a knowledge management project. Meanwhile, the complexity of what knowledge means has led to different approaches to managing knowledge.

In a climate of increased external and internal pressures for improvement, the information needs of school teachers and administrators have never been greater, yet the perils of information overload are real. Schools, like most organizations, should learn and gain knowledge so as to enhance teacher competency. There are many sorts of knowledge, which need to be managed in schools. Cochran-Smith and Lytle (1999) provide a valuable distinction in the types of knowledge that inform practice: knowledge of practice, or information about student performance, and knowledge for practice, or information about best practice. Teachers develop and acquire different kinds of knowledge in school where knowledge management should be applied to facilitate managing teachers' knowledge.

Knowledge Management can also be used as an alternative strategy by schools to improve competitive performance. Petrides and Nodine (2003) consider broadly that knowledge management in education can be thought of as a framework or an approach that enables people within an organization to develop a set of practices to collect information and knowledge mentioned above and share what they know, leading to action that improves services and outcomes. In seeking to balance an organization's information culture and its technology culture, knowledge management brings together three core organizational resources – people, processes and technologies- to enable the organization to use and share information and knowledge more effectively. For people, organizations should promote policies and practices to help them share and manage knowledge. Knowledge Management builds upon collegial and professional teamwork by actively engaging people at many organizational levels in sharing with others what they know, and what they are learning. For processes, Petrides and Nodine (2003) reminded us that formal and informal administrative procedures, curriculum development processes, information sharing patterns, information silos, salary incentives, award schemes and many other work practices affect information flow within every organization. Knowledge Management initiatives help to establish robust processes that enable people to get the information they need when they need it, as well as to share it with others who may benefit from it. Knowledge Management can help to promote those processes that lead to a more informed decision making. For technologies, Petrides & Nodine (2003) state that it is the most effective platform for target groups to access and exchange useful information across departments. Therefore, knowledge management can be used to better manage knowledge for schools not only by building up people networks but by also enriching knowledge in school communities by processes and technologies to improve school's competitive performance.

This study focused on instructors and university professors' perception of knowledge management implementation in schools from an organizational perspective. Instructors and university professors' understanding and expectations of knowledge management in the school environment were investigated.

METHODOLOGY

The study is based on the knowledge management framework of Rodrigues and Pai (2005). Developing a suitable knowledge management strategy is the key element of knowledge management implementation. The framework advocates a variety of knowledge management strategies as applied to different settings. In order to develop a suitable knowledge management strategy for schools, it is important

to identify the key factors or variables of knowledge management. The framework of Rodrigues and Pai (2005) was adopted. Rodrigues and Pai (2005) enumerate eight key factors and these are leadership and support, technology and infrastructure, knowledge creation, acquisition and learning, dissemination and transfer, application and exploitation, people competency and sharing culture. These eight dimensions include most typical knowledge management enablers and activators. This framework was developed and applied in an educational institution to measure knowledge management performance. This framework was adopted as the theoretical basis of the study to investigate the key factors of knowledge management implementation in the university.

The study was conducted in Quezon City University (QCU). Although the university has its own website, primarily offers courses in information technology, and tied up with the Korean-Philippine I.T Training Center and installed an Intranet system with efficient and user-friendly functions including e-mail, broadcast, uploading and downloading document, storing teaching and learning materials, monitoring student progress, and an e-learning platform for staff and students, little knowledge management has been initiated in the university. Besides, several servers have been installed for sharing files among teachers, and collaboration among teachers, such as “Lesson Study” for co-planning and co-evaluating the lessons in various subjects in the school have been launched for several years.

Because teachers are key players in organization knowledge creation (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995), they are the core subjects in this study, and understanding their perception of knowledge management is the focus of this research. All instructors and professors in QCU were invited to participate in a voluntary interview by means of returning a letter of consent to the researcher. Most of the instructors and professors (56 out of 63) were willing to participate. 33 respondents were randomly selected from the instructors and professors who were interested. The interview was conducted into two separate days, during the second semester of the academic year 2014-2015. Each interview lasted for about 20-30 minutes. All respondents’ answers were summarized and recorded. Respondents’ answers have been analyzed to identify the main points or themes occurring in the process. Respondents were identified using codes like A1 or B12, with letter A or B representing the interview days and the numbers representing the number of persons in the respective group.

To minimize any psychological stress and discomfort in the process, teachers participating in the study could withdraw at any time they liked. Furthermore, if any respondents did not feel comfortable or felt worry about the interview, they would be given the interview questions via facebook one evening before and the process of the interviews had been approved by the Quezon City University Human Resource Department. The interview questions were designed according to the framework adopted from Rodrigues and Pai’s (2005) the eight dimensions Knowledge Management enablers and activators model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Understanding of Knowledge Management

Most respondents did know the meaning of knowledge management, although their scope of knowledge management was not so broad and they did not know too much about knowledge management components. They mentioned some main points of knowledge management as follows:

Table 1
Analysis of the Response to the question: ‘Have you heard about knowledge management? What’s your understanding of knowledge management?’

Main points mentioned by respondent	Respondent
Knowledge sharing	A3, A4, B9, B10, B14, B18
Knowledge storage	A8, B16, B17, B18
Knowledge transfer	B6, B13
Conversion of Tacit Knowledge to Explicit Knowledge	A6, B12
Knowledge access	A8
Knowledge categorization	A1
Knowledge searching	B11
Protect knowledge	A12
Combine knowledge	A11
Update knowledge	B8

Most respondents regarded the most important function of knowledge management as the sharing and storage of knowledge. They were aware that knowledge could be an asset of an organization. This knowledge had its value and should be stored, shared and even protected to prevent the loss of knowledge from the organization. They also realized that knowledge should be converted from tacit knowledge to explicit knowledge, so that it could be readily shared or transferred within the organization. This can be concluded say that they commended “Dissemination and Transfer” were most prominent in knowledge management. Some interviewees further thought about the reusability of the knowledge; they thought that the knowledge stored in the school should also be categorized, so that the searching of useful information and its retrieval could be easily achieved. Furthermore, knowledge also needed to be combined and updated for better use. Their ideas indicated that they knew the need of “Application and Exploitation” in knowledge management. However, the other knowledge management components, such as “Knowledge Creation” and “Acquisition and Learning” seemed to be neglected.

Concerns for Implementing Knowledge Management

Most interviewees were concerned about the implementation of knowledge management in university. They mentioned some main points of knowledge management implementation as follows:

Table 2
Analysis of the Response to the question: ‘What are your feelings about the implementation of knowledge management in your school? What are your concerns?’

Main points mentioned by respondent	Respondent
Knowledge sharing	A2, A4, A7, A8, A9, A11, A15, B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, B7, B8, B9, B10, B11, B12, B16, B17
Knowledge transfer	A5, A6
Knowledge capture and acquisition	A12, A13
IT support	A3, A6, A12

Support to instructors	A7, A9
Building up a knowledge base	A7, A10, B9
Culture	A2, B11, B17,
Mutual support	B1
Retention or loss of knowledge	A5

Most respondents emphasized there should be knowledge sharing when knowledge management would be implemented in the university. Respondents expected that teachers could share their experience in class teacher's work (A6), teaching method or best practice (A7), teaching experience (B5 and B10) and student personal information (B2). They seemed to demonstrate that they had self confidence and self efficacy in sharing experience. Some respondents thought that sharing could help them perform their job efficiently because teachers could use other teachers' experience (B7). They reflected positive attitudes or feelings towards knowledge sharing. Some respondents were aware that the materials shared might not be useful to all teachers (A15 and B16). Some respondents were also aware that teachers might not be willing to share their experience with others (A4) or teachers had no time to share (B10). They also expressed worries or negative feelings or attitudes towards knowledge sharing.

Respondents noted the need of sharing, transfer and retention of knowledge, otherwise knowledge would be lost when some teachers left the school (A5 and A6).

From the respondents' perspective, IT support was also important to promote the implementation of KM (A3, A6, A12). IT facilities should be strengthened, especially the forum and knowledge repository (storage space) (A7, A10, B9) to set up a platform for sharing and storing of knowledge. Although the school personnel were commonly using the intranet system, it was mostly used to send and receive emails and assignments. Its usage could be exploited. Moreover, the system should be well designed to be user friendly and conveniently and commonly used in daily practice. Culture was also regarded as important in the implementation of KM (A2, B11, B17). The respondents mentioned learning culture (A2), consensus (B11) and sharing culture (B17). A culture with a common positive attitude to learning and sharing was thought to be essential to the implementation of knowledge management. These opinions showed their feelings about inadequate conditions of IT support and culture for knowledge management. University should address their needs by improvement in IT support and culture.

Some respondents thought that knowledge management could help experienced teachers transfer their experience to novice teachers, especially teaching methods, best practice and the knowledge that could not be easily learned from courses, such as skills in managing students' behavior (A7 and A9). The need for mentoring was expressed.

Finally, one respondents expressed that knowledge sharing could also bring mutual support to teachers (B1). It showed the positive elements of knowledge management.

The points mentioned above were those offered by respondents about the implementation of knowledge management in this university.

Prerequisites for Implementing Knowledge Management

Most respondents mentioned the prerequisites for support of implementation of knowledge management in school. They mentioned some main prerequisites for support of knowledge management implementation as follows:

Table 3

Analysis of the Response to the question: ‘To put KM into action, we need support from different quarters, such as people, culture, management and IT (explain if possible). What are the issues you think more important for putting KM into action in your school, and why are they important?’

Main points mentioned by respondent	Respondent
All (people, culture, management and IT)	A2, A3, A13, B11
People	A7, A8, A9, A10, A11, A12, B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, B13, B14
Culture	A6, A15, B6, B7, B8, B12, B15, B16, B17, B18
IT support	A4, A5, A15, B10
Management	A14

Some respondents thought that people, culture, management and IT were all important for knowledge management to be implemented successfully in schools (A2, A3, A13, B11). However, out of the four conditions of knowledge management implementation, most of the respondents regarded “people” (A7, A8, A9, A10, A11, A12, B1, B2, B3, B4, B5, B13, B14) and “culture” (A6, A15, B6, B7, B8, B12, B15, B16, B17, B18) as the two most important conditions of knowledge management implementation. These two conditions were quite related and mutually dependent. Therefore, if the school personnel would like to implement knowledge management in university, they should firstly change the perceptions or attitudes of people and the culture of the organization. Respondents reflected that they needed communication and interaction to understand the benefits of knowledge management, and they pointed out that the school personnel needed to convince staff to be involved in knowledge management. They noted that they also needed trust to encourage knowledge sharing and coordination is required to balance the conflict of interests. Respondents concluded that a culture of willingness to share their own knowledge and trusting each other are very important for implementing knowledge management. Some respondents reflected that at present the culture to allow knowledge sharing in the researched school at present has not yet been established and they understood that such culture would need considerable time to be inculcated. The opinions above showed the importance and readiness of knowledge management components of “People Competency” and “Sharing Culture”, as well as “Leadership and Support”.

IT support was also regarded by respondents as a condition for knowledge management implementation, such as “categorization of knowledge” and “storage and retrieval” (A4, A5, A15, B10). Some respondents also complained that the existing system failed to serve teachers neither for knowledge sharing nor for daily practice, and it should be upgraded. The opinions can be regarded as the importance of another knowledge management components “Technology and Infrastructure”.

Finally, management support was also regarded as necessary for implementation of knowledge management (A14) but not as important as other conditions. The respondents pointed out that leadership and top management support would empower staff to implement knowledge management actively. This belonged to the knowledge management components of “Leadership and Support”.

Expected Outcomes of Knowledge Management

Most respondents expressed the expected outcomes of knowledge management in university. They mentioned some main expected outcomes of knowledge management implementation as follows:

Table 4
Analysis of the Response to the question: ‘What do you expect to achieve from promoting and implementing KM in your school?’

Main points mentioned by respondent	Respondent
Learning experience from others	A1, A4, A6, A7, A9, A11, A12, B5, B7, B15
Sharing knowledge	A4, A5, B11, B12, B14, B17, B18
Time saving, efficient work	A4, A5, A10, A13, A15, B17
Getting useful information	A8, A15, B1, B2, B8, B10
Benefits to students	A3, A4, A14, B13
Self enhancement	A2, B4
Sharing culture	A5, B9
Problems Solving	A7
Enhancing Harmony and Communication	A3
Materials storage for future use	B4

Most respondents emphasized knowledge sharing when knowledge management would be implemented in school. Most interviewees noted that knowledge management could help them learn experience from others (A1, A4, A6, A7, A9, A11, A12, B5, B7, B15) and acquire shared knowledge (A4, A5, B11, B12, B14, B17, B18). They felt that knowledge management could allow them to acquire experience and knowledge to improve their practice. They would be more efficient and competent in their practice (A4, A5, A10, A13, A15, B17), and their teaching performance would improve. They felt that it could also help them get information they needed (A8, A15, B1, B2, B8, B10). This could make their practice beneficial to students (A3, A4, A14, B13). Respondents thought that teachers would also gain self enhancement from the knowledge they acquired (A2, B4). They also felt that a sharing culture would be built up (A5, B9) to facilitate further knowledge sharing. Some respondents pointed out that knowledge management could help problem solving (A7), enhancing harmony and communication and building up storage of material for future use (B4). They mostly thought that knowledge management could empower their competency to enhance their productivity. They seemed to express their eagerness and positive attitude towards knowledge management. It may be advantageous to develop “People Competency” and “Sharing Culture” in knowledge management implementation in future.

As an initial investigation of knowledge management implementation in a selected local university, this study investigated instructors and professors’ perceptions of KM implementation via interviews. Most existing research has investigated knowledge management in schools from the point of view of experts or even outsiders, and few studies have investigated teachers as end user’s of knowledge management implementation. Therefore, the results might help us understand knowledge management in the school environment from the participants’ viewpoint. This study might also serve as a diagnostic step in further study of knowledge management in university, example, developing a better understanding of key problems to be dealt with in knowledge management implementation in schools. Based on the literature review, designed interview questions were prepared and conducted interviews in the university in this study. The interview involved 4 questions to study teachers’ perceptions of knowledge management implementation: Understanding of knowledge management, Concerns of knowledge management, Needs for Support of knowledge management and Expected Outcomes of knowledge management.

From the respondents’ response to the question of “Understanding of Knowledge Management”, the study found that respondents recognized knowledge management was important for organization to

manage knowledge as an asset that can be stored, shared, transferred or transformed among members. They could know that “Dissemination and Transfer” and “Application and Exploitation” were the essential knowledge management components, but they might have neglected the essence of other knowledge management components such as “Knowledge Creation” and “Acquisition and Learning”. Therefore, some formal and systematic training may be necessary to help teachers realize the overall picture of knowledge management. From the results of the question of “Concerns of Knowledge Management”, it is found that respondents did emphasize the benefits of knowledge sharing and also showed their self confidence and self efficacy in knowledge sharing in their daily practice, as well as showing their worries and drawbacks concerning knowledge management implementation. More collaboration could be organized to provide opportunities for sharing among teachers to strengthen their confidence and positive attitudes towards knowledge management as well as strengthening the trust among staff so as to minimize negative feelings. Respondents further pointed out that IT support and culture were also critical but inadequate to promote knowledge management implementation and therefore they needed to be improved. In the part on “Prerequisites for Support of Knowledge Management”, IT and culture support together with people and management support, which were the key knowledge management components: “Technology and Infrastructure”, “Sharing Culture”, “People Competency” and “Leadership and Support” were further noted for their importance in facilitating knowledge management implementation. Among them, people and culture were most frequently mentioned among respondents. Actually, people and culture were regarded in this study as closely related and mutually dependent conditions. Respondents reflected that communication, interaction and trust among teachers did foster building up a community with a sharing culture in schools for knowledge management implementation. Respondents also expressed that the school needed to enhance the four knowledge management components as conditions for knowledge management implementation. For the part on “Expected Outcomes of Knowledge Management”, most respondents expected that knowledge management could help them acquire information, experience and knowledge from others to improve their practice and enhance their competence and efficiency in their work. Moreover, knowledge management was believed to enhance the building up of a sharing culture, which emphasizes organizational problem-solving, collegiality and shared resources in school. They showed their positive attitude to knowledge management and may welcome knowledge management implementation in future.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the eight key components in the framework of the study can help us understand teacher’s perceptions of knowledge management in school. From this study, we can note that the four knowledge management components: “Knowledge Creation”, “Acquisition and Learning”, “Dissemination and Transfer”, “Application and Exploitation” are the *Process Components* of the knowledge management components and the other four components: “Leadership and Support”, “Technology and Infrastructure”, “People Competency” and “Sharing Culture” are the *Condition Components* of the knowledge management components. Schools need to provide training to teachers to allow them learn more about the process components, so that teachers could have better “People Competency” and “Sharing Culture”. Moreover, the other *Condition Components*: “Leadership and Support” and “Technology and Infrastructure” should also be strengthened to facilitate knowledge management implementation. Both *Process Components* and *Condition Components* need to be addressed in order to foster teachers’ positive attitudes, feelings or perceptions towards knowledge management and minimize those worries or other negative attitudes, feelings or perceptions and in turn facilitate knowledge management implementation.

Because of the limitations of the interview, the results of this research might not be valid in other scenarios. However, the study contributed to new knowledge by examining perceptions of instructors and

university professors as end users of knowledge management implementation in a school environment. Since most other research has been performed to develop theoretical approaches, or has investigated knowledge management implementation on a larger scale involving a number of schools, little research has been done concerning teacher's perception in a designated school. The research is valuable as it deepens the understanding of knowledge management in schools regarding preparation for its implementation. These findings in turn provide insight into the further study of knowledge management implementation in schools. In this research, some issues are still unresolved, for example: "Do subjects and gender really influence teacher's attitude to team work and technology in Knowledge Management?" Different methods, such as focus group interviews and surveys, should be further used in this study. Also, further studies should be conducted in other schools with different backgrounds and characteristics in order to validate the results we found in this study, so that a more complete picture of knowledge management implementation in a school environment can be viewed.

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